

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Natural sources as promising future anticancer therapies - A review

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Abstract

Cancer is the second leading cause of death worldwide. The alternative natural therapies are required as they considered to have less toxic side effects compared to current chemotherapy. In the current review Web Science, PubMed, Scopus and Science Direct, were searched to provide information about medicinal plants that have shown anticancer activity against various forms of cancer.

Keywords: Cancer; Natural Products; Plants; Pharmacology

1. Introduction

Cancer is one of the second leading causes of morbidity and mortality globally. The current trend in cancer management requires the use of alternative treatments since the majority of anticancer drugs are known to be costly, with unwanted side effects. Recently, many medicinal plants inhibited proliferation, induced apoptosis, suppressed angiogenesis, inhibited invasiveness and metastasis⁽¹⁻⁷⁾. The current review highlighted the naturally-derived therapies as promising anticancer treatments.

2. Plants with anticancer effects

Cardenolide compounds isolated from the seeds of *Adonis aestivalis* showed activity against HSC-2, HSC-3, HSC-4, and HL-60 cells⁽⁸⁻⁹⁾. *Ailanthus altissima* showed activity against HeLa, MCF-7, MDA-MB-231, HepG2 and A549 cells guinea pig ear keratinocytes, human glial tumor cell line SF188, Epstein-Barr virus early antigen activation introduced by 12-O-tetradecanoylphorbol-13-acetate in Raji cells, human hepatoma cell lines, human leukemia (Jurkat), thyroid carcinoma (ARO and NPA), and hepatocellular carcinoma (HuH7) cell lines⁽¹⁰⁻¹⁸⁾. *Alhagi maurorum* possessed anticancer activity against human leukemia cell line (HL-60)⁽¹⁹⁻²⁰⁾. *Allium* species exerted anticancer activity against wide range of chemically induced cancers and wide range of tumor cell lines⁽²¹⁻⁵⁴⁾. *Althaea officinalis* possessed anticancer effect against tumoral lymphocytes⁽⁵⁵⁻⁵⁶⁾. *Althaea rosea* showed cytotoxicity against brine shrimp⁽⁵⁵⁻⁵⁶⁾. *Ammannia baccifera* possessed antitumor activity against HeLa cancer cell line⁽⁵⁸⁻⁵⁹⁾. *Anagyris foetida* exerted cytotoxic effect against HL-60 and LoVo cell lines⁽⁶⁰⁾. *Anchusa italic* possessed activity against MCF-7, HepG2, WEHI, MDBK and HepG2 cell line⁽⁶¹⁻⁶³⁾. *Antirrhinum majus* showed cytotoxic and haemolytic activity against human red blood cells⁽⁶⁴⁻⁶⁵⁾. *Apium graveolens* possessed antitumor activity against human DLA, Dalton's lymphoma ascites cell line; L929 and Mouse lung fibroblast⁽⁶⁶⁻⁶⁷⁾. *Arctium lappa* showed antiproliferative effects against Caco-2 cells and promyelocytic leukemia (HL60)⁽⁶⁸⁻⁶⁹⁾. *Aristolochia maurorum* exerted cytotoxicity on brine shrimp test⁽⁷⁰⁾. *Artemisia campestris* possessed cytotoxicity on HT-29 cell lines⁽⁷¹⁻⁷²⁾. *Arundo donax* was used in combination with *Spartium junceum* and *Cynodon dactylon* for the treatment of tumors⁽⁷³⁻⁷⁴⁾. *Asclepias curassavica* showed anticancer effect against human nasopharynx, HepG2 and Raji cell lines⁽⁷⁵⁻⁷⁸⁾. *Asparagus officinalis* possessed activity against human A2780, HO-8910, Eca-109, MGC-803, CNE, LTEP-a-2, KB and mouse L1210 tumor cells, also against HepG2 cells, human leukemia HL-60 cells, breast, colon and pancreatic

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cancers⁽⁷⁹⁻⁸⁵⁾. *Astragalus hamosus* exerted antiproliferative effect against HL-60/Dox, human acute lymphoid leukemia and two breast carcinoma cell lines MCF-7 estrogen receptor (ER) positive and MDA-MB 231 - ER negative⁽⁸⁶⁻⁹⁰⁾. *Bauhinia variegata* possessed anticancer effect against Dalton's ascitic lymphomas, skin papilloma, human epithelial larynx cancer, human breast cancer (HBL-100) cells and N-nitrosodiethylamine induced experimental liver tumor in rats⁽⁹¹⁻⁹⁵⁾. *Bellis perennis* showed cytotoxicity in potato disc tumor induction bioassay⁽⁹⁶⁻⁹⁸⁾. *Betula alba* possessed anticancer effects against neuroblastoma, rhabdomyosarcoma-medulloblastoma, glioma, thyroid, breast, lung, colon carcinoma, leukemia, multiple myeloma, ovarian carcinoma, cervical carcinoma, glioblastoma multiforme, A431 (skin epidermoid carcinoma), A2780 (ovarian carcinoma), HeLa (cervix adenocarcinoma) and MCF7 (breast adenocarcinoma), liver metastatic murine colon 26-L5 carcinoma cells, WI-38 fibroblast cells, VA-13 malignant tumor cells and K562 tumor cell line⁽⁹⁹⁻¹⁰⁴⁾. *Bidens tripartita* exerted antitumor effect against mouse leukemia cells⁽¹⁰⁵⁻¹⁰⁶⁾. *Brassica rapa* possessed antiproliferative effect against human lung cancer A-549 cell line, Hep-2, AMN-3, HCT-116, MCF-7, HeLa, and MCF cancer cells⁽¹⁰⁷⁻¹¹²⁾. *Bryonia dioica* exerted anticancer effect against Burkitt's lymphoma BL41 cell lines⁽¹¹³⁾, and *Bryophyllum calycinum* against Ehrlich ascites carcinoma (EAC)⁽¹¹⁴⁻¹¹⁵⁾. *Bryophyllum calycinum* inhibited the occurrence of Ehrlich ascites carcinoma (EAC)⁽¹¹⁴⁻¹¹⁵⁾. *Caccinia crassifolia* showed antitumor activity against MCF7, HepG2, WEHI164 cancer cell lines⁽¹¹⁶⁾. *Caesalpinia crista* inhibited the growth of Ehrlich ascites carcinoma, possessed cytotoxicity in brine shrimp lethality test and showed anticancer effect against T47D, DU145, MCF-7 (breast adenocarcinoma), DU145 (prostate carcinoma), C33A (cervical carcinoma) and Vero (African green monkey kidney fibroblast) cells⁽¹¹⁷⁻¹²¹⁾. *Calendula officinalis* inhibited the multiplication of L929 and HepG2, colon cancer, leukemia, melanoma, human skin fibroblast (HSF), human breast cancer cells (T47D), leukemias, melanomas, fibrosarcomas and cancers of breast, prostate, cervix, lung, pancreas, colorectal cells (*in vitro*) and Ando-2 melanoma cells (*in vivo*)⁽¹²²⁻¹²⁶⁾. *Calotropis procera* inhibited the growth of Hep2, Vero cell lines, COLO 320 tumor cells, HL-60, CEM (human leukemia), HCT-8 (human colon cancer), B-16/F10 (murine melanoma) and many other cell lines⁽¹²⁷⁻¹³⁵⁾. *Canna indica* showed cytotoxicity in brine shrimp toxicity test⁽¹³⁶⁻¹³⁷⁾. *Capparis spinosa* inhibited the multiplication of hepatoma HepG2, breast cancer MCF-7 cells, human epidermoid larynx carcinoma, human cervix uterine epitheloid carcinoma, SGC-7901 cells and Ehrlich Ascites carcinoma⁽¹³⁸⁻¹⁴⁴⁾. *Capsella bursa-pastoris* possessed anticancer effect against Ehrlich tumour in mice, MH134, L1210 mouse tumor cells and HSC-2 human oral cancer cells⁽¹⁴⁵⁻¹⁴⁹⁾. *Capsicum species* exerted anticancer effect against Hep-G2 cells, oral tumor cell lines (HSC-2, HSG), and TE-13 (esophageal squamous cell carcinoma) cell line⁽¹⁵⁰⁻¹⁵⁴⁾. *Carthamus tinctorius* possessed antiproliferative effect against SW620, Hep2, MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cell, S180 Sarcoma, LA795 lung cancer in mice and skin tumor induced by 7, 12-dimethylbenz [a]anthracene⁽¹⁵⁵⁻¹⁵⁹⁾. *Casuarina equisetifolia* showed cytotoxicity in brine shrimp lethality test⁽¹⁰⁻¹⁶¹⁾ and *Celosia cristata* possessed antiproliferative effect against HeLa, Cos 7, HepG2, SK-Hep1 and LS 174T cell lines⁽¹⁶²⁻¹⁶³⁾. *Chenopodium album* induced anticancer activity against estrogen dependent (MCF-7) and estrogen independent (MDA-MB-468) human breast cancer cell lines⁽¹⁶⁴⁻¹⁶⁵⁾. *Chrozophora tinctoria* possessed cytotoxicity against brine shrimp assay and inhibited the proliferation of mouse skin tumors induced by 7, 12-Dimethylbenzene (a) anthracene (DMBA)⁽¹⁶⁶⁻¹⁶⁷⁾. *Cicer arietinum* possessed anticancer effect against oral cancer cells and MCF-7 breast cancer cell line⁽¹⁶⁹⁻¹⁷⁰⁾. *Cichorium intybus* showed antitumor activity in Ehrlich ascites carcinoma in mice, dimethylbenz[a]anthracene (DMBA) induced benign breast tumors and against human leukemia HL-60, U-937, melanoma C32, human prostate cancer PC-3 cells, human breast carcinoma T47D cells and colon cancer RKO cells⁽¹⁷²⁻¹⁷⁶⁾. *Citrullus colocynthis* was active against ER+ MCF-7 and ER- MDA-MB-231 human breast cancer cell lines⁽¹⁷⁷⁻¹⁷⁸⁾. While, *Citrus* species showed antiproliferative effect against human breast carcinoma cell line (MDA-MB-453), human lymphoblastoid B cell line, human pancreatic cancer cells, human larynx, cervix, breast, liver, colon cancer cell lines, and human astrocytoma cancer cells⁽¹⁷⁹⁻¹⁹¹⁾. *Clerodendron inerme* possessed anticancer effect against 7, 12-dimethyl Benz (a) anthracene (DMBA) induced skin carcinogenesis in mice and hamster buccal pouch carcinogenesis⁽¹⁹²⁻¹⁹⁵⁾. *Clitoria ternatea* exerted antitumor activity against hormone-dependent breast cancer cell line (MCF-7), non-hormone-dependent breast cancer cell line (MDA-MB-231), human ovary cancer cell line (Caov-3), human cervical cancer cell line (Hela), human liver cancer cell line (HepG2), human foreskin fibroblast cell line (Hs27) and Dalton's lymphoma (DLA) induced in mice⁽¹⁹⁶⁻²⁰⁰⁾. *Convolvulus arvensis* showed anticancer effect against human tumor cell line (Hela), lymphoblastic leukemia, Jurkat cells, human Rhabdomyosarcoma (RD) tumor cell line and 7-12-dimethyl benz(a)anthracene (DMBA) induced skin carcinogenesis⁽²⁰¹⁻²⁰⁵⁾. *Convolvulus scammonia* was active against mice implanted with hepatic cancer cells (hepatic cell H22) and CHO cell line⁽²⁰⁶⁻²⁰⁸⁾. Epidermal carcinoma of nasopharynx cells, human breast cancer cell lines (MDA-MB-231 and MCF-7), melanoma cells (B16F10, SK-MEL-28, and A375), leukemic cell lines U937, HL-60 and myelogenous leukemia cell line K562⁽²⁰⁹⁻²¹⁴⁾. *Corchorus capsularis* showed cytotoxicity in brine shrimp test⁽²¹⁵⁻²¹⁶⁾. *Coriandrum sativum* possessed anticancer effects against MCF-7, BMK (kidney), KHOS-2405 (bone), WRL-68 (liver) and L5178Y-R lymphoma cells⁽²¹⁷⁻²²⁰⁾. *Coronilla scorpioides* showed cytotoxicity in brine shrimp and potato disk assays⁽²²¹⁻²²²⁾. While, *Coronilla varia* possessed growth inhibitory activity against F7 and KB cell lines⁽²²³⁻²²⁷⁾. *Cotoneaster racemiflora* showed cytotoxicity in brine shrimp test⁽²²⁸⁻²²⁹⁾. HeLa cells, colorectal cancer cell lines (HCT-116, SW-480, and HT-29), carcinomic human alveolar basal epithelial cells, HepG2, human transitional cell carcinoma (TCC), lung cancer cells (A549), ovarian cancer HO-8910 cells, transplanted sarcoma-180 (S-180), Ehrlich ascites carcinoma (EAC) and Dalton's lymphoma ascites (DLA) tumours in mice⁽²³⁰⁻²⁴⁷⁾. *Cuminum cyminum* showed anticancer effect against HeLa cells,

benzo(α)pyrene [B(α)P]-induced forestomach tumorigenesis, 3-methylcholanthrene (MCA)- induced uterine cervix tumorigenesis in mice, B[a]P-induced neoplasia and 3' MeDAB induced hepatomas in rats⁽²⁴⁸⁻²⁵²⁾. *Cupressus sempervirens* possessed antiproliferative effect on melanotic melanoma C32 cells, renal adenocarcinoma cells and human BPH-stromal cells⁽²⁵³⁻²⁵⁵⁾. *Cuscuta planiflora* showed cytotoxicity in brine shrimp test and inhibited the growth of human breast carcinoma (MDA-MB-468), human colorectal adenocarcinoma (HT29) and human uterine cervical carcinoma (Hela) cell lines⁽²⁵⁶⁻²⁵⁸⁾. *Cydonia oblonga* exerted anticancer effect against human HepG2, A549, HeLa cell lines, human kidney and colon cancer cells⁽²⁵⁹⁻²⁶¹⁾. *Cynodon dactylon* inhibited the growth of Ehrlich ascites carcinoma and ascitic lymphoma (ELA) in mice, in addition it possessed cytotoxicity against (COLO 320 DM, MCH-7, AGS, and A549)⁽²⁶²⁻²⁶⁵⁾. *Cyperus rotundus* showed cytotoxicity in brine shrimp test and inhibited the growth of Ehrlich ascites carcinoma cells, brain tumor cell line, Hela (cervix carcinoma cell line), ovarian cancer (A2780, SKOV3 and OVCAR3), endometrial cancer (Hec1A and Ishikawa) cells and human breast carcinoma MDA-MB-231 cell model⁽²⁶⁶⁻²⁷⁰⁾. *Dactyloctenium aegyptium* showed anticancer effect against human hepatocellular carcinoma cells (HepG-2), colon carcinoma cells (HCT-116), breast carcinoma cells (MCF-7), human lung cancer (A549) and cervical cancer (HeLa) cells⁽²⁷¹⁻²⁷³⁾. *Datura metel* exerted antitumor effect against A549 (lung), BGC-823 (gastric), K562 (leukemia) cancer cell lines, vero cell line, human lung carcinoma cells (A549), human colorectal adenocarcinoma cells (DLD-1), HepG-2, HeLa and SGC-7901 cell lines⁽²⁷⁴⁻²⁷⁸⁾. *Daucus carota* showed anticancer effect against wide range of cancer cells including lung, skin, breast, glioblastoma cancer cell, skin papilloma, myeloid leukemia (AML) cells, CaCo-2 cells, human lymphoid leukaemia cells, myeloid and lymphoid leukemia cells, human breast adenocarcinoma cells, MDA-MB-231, MCF-7, human colon adenocarcinoma cells (HT-29 and Caco-2) and HepG-2 cell lines⁽²⁷⁹⁻²⁹¹⁾. *Delphinium brunonianum* inhibited the growth of Vero, MDCK cell lines and hepatoma cell line⁽²⁹²⁻²⁹³⁾. *Desmostachya bipinnata* showed cytotoxicity in brine shrimp test and anticancer effect against HCT-116 colon cancer cell line, human cervical cancer cell lines (HeLa), human laryngeal epithelial carcinoma cells (HEP-2) and NIH 3T3⁽²⁹⁴⁻²⁹⁷⁾. *Dianthus caryophyllus* inhibited the proliferation of colon cancer cells⁽²⁹⁸⁻²⁹⁹⁾. *Digitalis* species possessed antiproliferative effects against myeloma cell line RPMI8226/5 and its sublines RPMI8226/DOX40 and RPMI8226fLR-5, the lymphoma cell lines U-937GTB and U-937Vcr, the small-cell lung cancer cell line NCI-H69 and its subline NCI-H69AR, renal adenocarcinoma cell line ACHN, the leukemia cell line CCRF-CEM and its subline CCRF-CEM/VM-1, prostate, melanoma, pancreatic, leukaemia, neuroblastoma, and tumors of urinary, respiratory cancer and many other cancers cells⁽³⁰⁰⁻³²²⁾. *Dodonaea viscosa* showed antiproliferative effect against breast carcinoma cell line⁽³²³⁻³²⁴⁾. While, *Lablab purpureus* showed cytotoxicity in brine shrimp test⁽³²⁵⁻³²⁷⁾. *Echinochloa crus-galli* inhibited the proliferation of MCF-7 (breast cells), HCT-116 (colon cells), HELA (cervical cells), HEPG-2 (liver cells), HCT-116 and HeLa cell lines⁽³²⁸⁻³³⁰⁾. *Equisetum arvense* exerted anticancer effect against human cancer cell lines HeLa, HT-29, and MCF7, human leukemic U 937 cells, melanoma B16 cells, cervical adenocarcinoma, lung fibroblast, breast adenocarcinoma, and human embryonic kidney cells⁽³³¹⁻³³⁷⁾. *Erigeron Canadensis* possessed anticancer effect against human cervix adenocarcinoma (HeLa), skin carcinoma (A431), and breast adenocarcinoma (MCF-7) cells⁽³³⁸⁻³⁴³⁾. *Erodium cicutarium* inhibited the proliferation of colon cancer cells (Caco-2)⁽³⁴⁴⁾. *Eryngium creticum* inhibited the growth of MCF7 breast cancer cell line and HeLa cell line⁽³⁴⁵⁻³⁴⁸⁾. *Eucalyptus* species possessed anticancer effects against wide range of cell lines including human colon cancer cell lines HCT116, RKO, human ECV-304 cell lines, WEHI-3, HT-29, HL-60 cell lines, MCF-7, Hep-2, HepG-2, HeLa, HCT-116, Caco-2 cell lines, liver, lung, prostate and breast cell lines⁽³⁴⁹⁻³⁵⁸⁾. *Eupatorium cannabinum* showed antiproliferative effect against colon cancer cell line HT29, leukaemia, ZNS tumor cells (V 251), DLD-1, CCRF-CEM, HL-60 cell lines, Jurkat cell line and Ehrlich ascites tumour cells⁽³⁵⁸⁻³⁶⁶⁾. *Euphorbia hirta* showed cytotoxicity in brine shrimp test and possessed anticancer effect against human epidermoid carcinoma KB 3-1 cells⁽³⁶⁷⁻³⁶⁹⁾. *Euphorbia macroclada* inhibited the growth of MDA-MB-468 cell line⁽³⁶⁹⁾. *Fagopyrum esculentum* possessed anticancer effect against Hep G2 (hepatoma) cells, L1210 (leukemia) cells, breast cancer (MCF-7) cells, human mammary cancer cell Bcap37, human leukemia U937 cells, mammary tumor and colon tumors in rats⁽³⁷⁰⁻³⁷⁵⁾. *Ficus carica* exerted antitumor activity against esophageal cancer line, breast cancer cell lines (MCF7), (Hep3b: Hepatocellular carcinoma; Hela: cervical epithelial cancer; PC-3: prostate cancer) cell lines, MCF-7, HepG-2, U2OS cell lines, T98G, U-138 MG, U-87 MG glioblastoma multiforme cell lines and human melanoma cells⁽³⁷⁶⁻³⁸³⁾. *Ficus cunia* protected from the formation of micronuclei cells induced by cyclophosphamide in bone marrow of mice⁽³⁸⁴⁾. *Ficus religiosa* showed cytotoxicity in brine shrimp test and possessed anticancer effects against cervical cancer cell lines SiHa (HPV16 positive), HeLa (HPV18 positive) and human breast cancer cells⁽³⁸⁵⁻³⁹¹⁾. The anethole isolated from *Foeniculum vulgare* possessed anticancer effect against Ehrlich ascites tumour in mice⁽³⁹²⁻³⁹³⁾. Isopimaric acid, 15-Dien-19-oic acid, extracted from the bulbs of *Fritillaria imperialis* inhibited the growth of cervical cancer cell line and HeLa cells⁽³⁹⁴⁾. *Fumaria officinalis* showed cytotoxicity in brine shrimp lethality bioassay⁽³⁹⁵⁻³⁹⁶⁾. *Galium aparine* possessed anticancer effect against human breast cancer cells (MCF-7), human colon cancer cells (Caco-2) and MCF-7 cell line⁽³⁹⁷⁻⁴⁰⁰⁾. *Galium verum* inhibited the growth of neck cancer cell lines HLaC78 and FADU⁽⁴⁰¹⁻⁴⁰³⁾. *Glossostemon bruguieri* possessed antiproliferative effects against hepatocellular (HCC), HepG2 and Hep3B cell lines⁽⁴⁰⁴⁻⁴⁰⁵⁾. *Glycyrrhiza glabra* showed antitumor activity against intestinal carcinoma (Caco-2) and prostate carcinoma (PC-3) cell lines^(406, 407). *Gnaphalium luteoalbum* possessed cytotoxic activity against mouse fibroblasts (NIH3T3), healthy monkey kidney (VERO) and four human cancer cell lines (gastric, AGS; colon, HT-29; and breast, MCF-7 and MDAMB-231)⁽⁴⁰⁸⁻⁴¹⁰⁾. Gossypol isolated from *Gossypium* species showed antiproliferative effect on a number of cancer cells including adrenal,

prostate, mammary carcinomas, gliomas, endometriosis, uterine myoma, MCF-7 WT, MCF-7 ADR and human melanoma cell lines (SK-mel-19 and SK-mel-28)⁽⁴¹¹⁻⁴¹⁶⁾. *Haplophyllum* species exhibited antitumor activities against liver carcinoma (HEPG2) and lung carcinoma cell line (H1299)⁽⁴¹⁷⁻⁴¹⁸⁾. *Hedera helix* possessed cytotoxic activity on the brine shrimp bioassay and showed anti-proliferative effect against Mat-LyLu cells (strongly metastatic), AT-2 cells (weakly metastatic) and mouse B16 melanoma cell lines⁽⁴¹⁹⁻⁴²⁰⁾. *Helianthus annuus* showed antiproliferative effect against HeLa, MCF-7 and A-431 cell lines⁽⁴²¹⁻⁴²²⁾. *Helianthus tuberosus* showed cytotoxic activities against MCF-7, A549, HeLa cancer, Hp G2- cells, HCT-116, MCF-7 and 1301- cell lines⁽⁴²³⁻⁴²⁵⁾. *Herniaria hirsute* possessed cytotoxic properties against MCF7 (breast carcinoma), NCI H460 (non-small cell lung carcinoma), HeLa (cervical carcinoma), HepG2 (hepatocellular carcinoma) and PLP2 (porcine liver cells)⁽⁴²⁶⁻⁴²⁷⁾. *Hibiscus cannabinus* exhibited cytotoxic effect towards human colorectal cancer cell lines (HT29), HeLa, Hep-2 and A-549 cell lines⁽⁴²⁸⁻⁴²⁹⁾. *Hibiscus rosa sinensis* possessed anticancer effect against leukaemic cancer cell line (K-562), and inhibited 7,12-dimethyl benz(a)anthracene (DMBA)/croton oil-mediated carcinogenesis in mouse skin via 12-O-tetradecanoyl phorbol-13-acetate (TPA)-induced tumour promotion response⁽⁴³⁰⁻⁴³²⁾. *Hibiscus sabdariffa* showed anticancer effects against wide range of cancer including N-nitrosomethylurea (NMU)-induced leukemia of rats, human promyelocytic leukemia (HL-60), melanoma cells, human prostate cancer LNCaP (lymph node carcinoma of the prostate) and HeLa cells cell line⁽⁴³³⁻⁴³⁹⁾. Grossamide, and cannabins D and G isolated from *Hyoscyamus niger* seeds exhibited moderate cytotoxicity in cultured LNCaP human prostate cancer cells⁽⁴⁴⁰⁻⁴⁴¹⁾. *Hypericum triquetrifolium* showed anticancer effect against human cancer cell lines, large cell lung carcinoma cell line COR-L23, hepatocellular carcinoma cell line HepG-2, renal cell adenocarcinoma ACHN, melanoma cell line C32, Vero cell lines, colon and lung (HCT-116, A549)⁽⁴⁴²⁻⁴⁴³⁾. *Inula graveolens* possessed antiproliferative against A549 and HL60 cells⁽⁴⁴⁴⁻⁴⁴⁵⁾. *Iris pallida* exhibited anti-proliferative activity in the NCI 60 human cancer cell lines, A2780 and K562 (drug-sensitive and a drug-resistant cell line)⁽⁴⁴⁶⁻⁴⁴⁸⁾. The ethanolic extract of *Jasminum sambac* inhibited the growth of Dalton's lymphoma ascites-induced lymphatic cancer in Swiss albino mice, Hep-2, MCF-7, and Vero cell lines⁽⁴⁴⁹⁻⁴⁵¹⁾. *Juglans regia* possessed anticancer effects against different human cancer cell lines [prostate colon (Colo-205 and HCT-116), breast (T47D), prostate (PC-3 and DU-145), skin (A-431) and lung (NCI-H322 and A549), DU145, MCF7 and TG/HAVSMC]⁽⁴⁵²⁻⁴⁵³⁾. *Juniperus communis* possessed cytotoxic activities against HepG2 cells, human prostate cancer cells (PC3), human colon cancer cells (HCT 116) and breast cancer cells (MCF7)⁽⁴⁵⁴⁻⁴⁵⁷⁾. The berries methanol extracts of *Juniperus oxycedrus* subsp. *oxycedrus* and *Juniperus oxycedrus* subsp. *macrocarpa* did not affect HepG2 cell viability and both were non-toxic against *Artemia salina*⁽⁴⁵⁸⁻⁴⁵⁹⁾. *Jussiaea repens* showed the highest cytotoxic activities against Ehrlich ascites carcinoma cells lines⁽⁴⁶⁰⁻⁴⁶²⁾. *Kochia scoparia* showed antiproliferation effect in oral squamous cell carcinoma, human breast cancer cells and HepG2 cell⁽⁴⁶³⁻⁴⁶⁵⁾. *Lagerstroemia indica* showed cytotoxicity against A549 (nonsmall cell lung carcinoma), SK-OV-3 (ovary malignant ascites), SK-MEL-2 (skin melanoma), and HCT-15 (colon adenocarcinoma)⁽⁴⁶⁶⁻⁴⁶⁷⁾. *Lagerstroemia speciosa* exhibited cytotoxicity against Dalton's Lymphoma Ascites cells (DLA), Ehrlich ascites carcinoma cells, HCT116 human colon cancer cells and MCF-7 cell lines⁽⁴⁶⁸⁻⁴⁷⁰⁾. *Lantana camara* showed anticancer effects against Jurkat leukemia cell, Vero cell, MCF-7 cell, HeLa cell and Ehrlich ascites carcinoma⁽⁴⁷¹⁻⁴⁷⁴⁾. *Lawsonia inermis* inhibited the growth of HCT-15 (human colon cancer cells), colon cancer COLO-205 cells, MCF-7, HeLa, HCT-116, and HT-29⁽⁴⁷⁵⁻⁴⁸⁰⁾. *Lepidium sativum* exhibited cytotoxic effects against colon, endometrium cancer cells, K562, human cancer cell lines such as human neuroblastoma cell line (IMR-32), colon cancer cell lines (HT-15 & HT-29), lung cancer cell line A-549, Hep2 and MCF-7 cell line⁽⁴⁸¹⁻⁴⁸⁵⁾. *Lippia nodiflora* possessed anticancer effect against MCF7 cells, human lung cancer cell line (NCI-H460), and Ehrlich's ascites carcinoma⁽⁴⁸⁶⁻⁴⁸⁸⁾. *Lithospermum officinale* inhibited the growth of NB4 cell line⁽⁴⁸⁹⁾. *Luffa acutangula* exhibited cytotoxic potential against human neuronal glioblastoma cells (U343), human lung cancer cells (A549 and NCI-H460) and Ehrlich ascites carcinoma (EAC) cell line⁽⁴⁹⁰⁻⁴⁹²⁾. *Luffa cylindrical* possessed cytotoxic effect in brine shrimp lethality assay and exhibited anticancer effect against hepatocellular carcinoma, breast cancer cell lines, acute myeloid leukemia, acute lymphocyte leukemia and colon cancer cells (HT-29 and HCT-15)⁽⁴⁹³⁻⁴⁹⁶⁾. *Lythrum salicaria* showed cytotoxic activities against colon carcinoma (HT-29), leukemia (K-562), breast ductal carcinoma (T47D), and T47D cancer cell lines⁽⁴⁹⁷⁻⁴⁹⁸⁾. *Mangifera indica* possessed anticancer activity against Molt-4 leukemia, A-549 lung, MDA-MB-231 breast, LnCap prostate, SW-480 colon cancer cells, and breast cancer cells (MDA-MB-231 and MCF-7)⁽⁴⁹⁹⁻⁵⁰¹⁾. *Marrubium vulgare* exhibited anticancer activity against Ehrlich tumor cell lines, human tumor cell lines U251 and MCF7 (brain tumor and breast carcinoma cell lines), HeLa cell lines, K562, K562R (imatinib-resistant), and 697 human leukemia cell lines⁽⁵⁰²⁻⁵⁰⁵⁾. *Medicago sativa* exhibited cytotoxic effects against sensitive and multidrug-resistant tumor cells lines [mouse leukaemia P388 cell line and its doxorubicin-resistant counterpart (P388/DOX)]⁽⁵⁰⁶⁻⁵⁰⁷⁾. *Melilotus officinalis* showed cytotoxicity in *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*-induced potato disk tumor assay⁽⁵⁰⁸⁾. *Mirabilis jalapa* possessed cytotoxicity in brine shrimp lethality bioassay and showed cytotoxicity against T47D and SiHa cell lines⁽⁵⁰⁹⁻⁵¹¹⁾. *Narcissus tazetta* possessed anticancer activity against MCF-7, Hep-2, Vero cell line, and against a panel of cancer cell lines⁽⁵¹²⁻⁵¹⁵⁾. *Nasturtium officinale* exhibited anticancer effect on HeLa cells and HT29 cells⁽⁵¹⁶⁻⁵¹⁷⁾. *Nerium oleander* possessed antitumor activity on Ehrlich ascites carcinoma cells line, human breast cancer (Pasteur, C203), HepG-2: human hepatocellular carcinoma (Pasteur, C124), human chronic myeloid Leukemia (Pasteur, C122) cell lines and liver cancer cell line (HEPG2)⁽⁵¹⁸⁻⁵²¹⁾. *Ocimum basilicum* possessed cytotoxicity in brine shrimp assay and showed anticancer effect against human cervix adenocarcinoma HeLa cells, human melanoma FemX cells, human chronic myelogenous

leukaemia K562 cells, human ovarian SKOV3 cells and against 7,12 dimethyl benz(a)anthracene (DMBA)-initiated skin papilloma⁽⁵²²⁻⁵²⁴⁾. *Ononis spinosa* showed anticancer effects against ovarian, breast, colon, liver, cervical, lung, bladder, gastric, esophagus, nasopharyngeal, adrenal medulla tumor, multiple myeloma, osteosarcoma, glioma⁽⁵²⁵⁻⁵²⁶⁾. *Onopordum acanthium* showed antiproliferative action on HL-60 leukemia cells, glioblastoma U-373 tumour cells, HeLa (cervix adenocarcinoma), MCF7 (breast adenocarcinoma) and A431 (skin epidermoid carcinoma)⁽⁵²⁷⁻⁵³⁰⁾. Polysaccharide isolated from *Orchis mascula* possessed anticancer activity against A549 lung and AGS human gastric carcinoma⁽⁵³¹⁻⁵³²⁾. *Ranunculus arvensis* exhibited cytotoxicity in brine shrimp lethality assay⁽⁵³³⁾. *Reseda lutea* showed significant antiproliferative effects against human A375 (melanoma) and MRC5 (fibroblast) cell lines⁽⁵³⁴⁾. While, *Reseda odorata* possessed anticancer effects against various types of human malignancies such as breast, colon, pancreatic, prostate, oral, lung, kidney, bladder, ovarian, cervical, placental, skin, liver, gastric, oesophageal cancers and glioblastoma⁽⁵³⁵⁻⁵³⁷⁾,

3. Conclusion

Many anticancer drugs are available for the treatment of cancer, and in most cases, they caused undesirable adverse effects. Many medicinal plants caused cell cycle arrest and inhibited angiogenesis in tumor cells in addition to induction of apoptosis and inhibition of invasiveness and metastasis. The current review highlighted the naturally-derived therapies as promising anticancer treatments.

Compliance with ethical standards

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